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STRENGTH 2024

**STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABILITY COMMUNICATION IN TOURISM,
HOSPITALITY, AND EVENT INDUSTRIES**

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Book of Abstracts

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Novi Sad, August 2024

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Contents

International Scientific Board	4
Sustainable Tourism Through Extended Reality: Lessons from Heritage Destinations in Serbia	5
Enhancing Sustainability Communication Through the Beverage Lens	6
Addressing Artificial Intelligence Bias in Accessible Smart Tourism for Sustainable Development ...	7
The Impact of Film as a Segment of Creative and Cultural Industries on Intangible Heritage and Tourism	9
Strengthening Digital Sustainability Communication in Tourism and Culture Between US and Serbia Through International Cooperation	10
The Digital Carbon Footprint of the Tourism, Hospitality, and Events Industries	11
Micro-Green Framework: Conceptualizing Green Skills Development Through Microlearning in the Workplace	13
Use of ICT in Museum Interpretation - Lessons from Serbia.....	15

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Strengthening Digital Sustainability Communication in Tourism and Culture Between US and Serbia Through International Cooperation

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Abstract: There are significant differences in the perceptions of sustainability and its importance in tourism and culture between the U.S. and Serbia. This paper examines the digital sustainability communication of U.S. entities in tourism and culture through the lens of international cooperation with Serbia. Specifically, using a mixed methodology, it assesses the effectiveness of various activities, including a preparatory online workshop on digital communication for sustainable tourism, field research on three exemplary case studies of sustainable practices in Florida, and three inclusive workshops held in Serbia. The findings indicate that these initiatives positively impact the effectiveness of sustainability communication among tourism stakeholders in both countries, fostering stronger cross-cultural connections and mutual understanding. Implications for further research are outlined.

Keywords: Sustainability Communication; International Cooperation; Tourism Marketing; USA; Serbia

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